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Policy Brief

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Change Log

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v2.0	15.08.25	Dorothea Dörr, Beatriz Serrano-Solano, Aastha Mathur, Arrate Muñoz-Barrutia, Anna Kreshuk, Florian Jug, Ilari Pulli	Revised draft accepted for submission

Acronyms and Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
BIA	Biolmage Archive
BMZ	Biolmage Model Zoo
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
RI	Research Infrastructure

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1. Introduction

Call: HORIZON-INFRA-2021-SERV-01

Topic: HORIZON-INFRA-2021-SERV-01-06 – Enabling research infrastructure services for better use of imaging data to address challenges in thematic research areas

Project: Artificial Intelligence for Image Data Analysis in the Life Sciences (AI4Life). <https://ai4life.eurobioimaging.eu/>

Project objectives:

Machine learning has enabled and accelerated frontier research in the life sciences, but democratised access to such methods is, unfortunately, not a given. Access to necessary hardware and software, data, knowledge, and training is limited, while methods and resources are typically insufficiently documented and often fail to comply with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data and Open Science principles. To address these challenges, the AI4Life project pursues the following objectives:

- **Provide democratised FAIR access to Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based image analysis methods through the [BioImage Model Zoo \(BMZ\)](#) AI model repository**, computationally powered by the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) infrastructure and optionally installable on-premise, so that life scientists without computational expertise can run advanced models with minimal effort.
- **Establish standards for the submission, storage, and FAIR access of reference data, reference annotations (ground-truth), trained AI models, and trainable AI methods in cooperation with the [BioImage Archive \(BIA\)](#) and the EOSC**, ensuring open and free virtual access for both academia and industry and full interoperability with other European RIs.
- **Offer a developer-facing BMZ service for simple model deployment, sharing, and dissemination of new AI-based methods**, greatly shortening the path from algorithm development to broad use, thus accelerating innovation in both academia and SMEs.
- **Organise Open Calls and Challenges** on high-impact imaging problems aligned with EU Mission areas and publish winning solutions in the BMZ.
- **Empower common image analysis platforms** such as Fiji, ilastik, ImJoy, deepImageJ, and ZeroCostDL4Mic through the integration of BMZ models for a broad and easy model reuse and improved image analysis workflows.
- **Organise targeted training events, workshops, and conference sessions for both life scientists and method developers**, working with multiple European Research Infrastructures (RI) to maximise community uptake across domains such as structural biology, medicinal chemistry, marine biodiversity, and plant science.

2. Policy implications and recommendations

2.1. Implementation of research infrastructures

AI4Life has developed and continues to improve the BMZ, an AI model repository that provides life scientists with democratised access to AI-based image analysis methods, AI ready image datasets, and FAIR image analysis infrastructure services in close cooperation with the BIA. These efforts also include the engagement of image analysis software and AI model developers as community partners.

Challenges:

- Limited computing resources and tools to efficiently access the resources available to the project consortium still represent a bottleneck on the way to allowing users to fully scale up image analysis through the BMZ website.
- Need for continuous community partner support, for instance, to facilitate the FAIRification and harmonisation of new model collections.

Recommendation 01: Implement Open Calls with cascading grants for developers and community partners to support tools and AI model interoperability and FAIRification for a community-spanning infrastructure implementation.

Recommendation 02: Cultivate community collaboration through the support of training and dissemination activities to gather community feedback, foster community engagement, and contributions to enhance research infrastructure capabilities.

2.2. Access to research infrastructures

AI4Life is supporting users (through direct support and helpdesk services) and developers (through contributor services) around the BMZ, improving accessibility of the infrastructure. Through the project's Open Calls for AI-based image analysis support, AI4Life attracted research users from more than 12 life science disciplines worldwide and from both academia and industry. As a result, the consortium has developed Open Call guidelines and best practices that will inform future access calls and programmes not only within the AI4Life infrastructure itself but also at Euro-Biolmaging and other partner RIs.

Recommendation 03: Recognise the benefits of direct user support for making image data and analysis methods FAIR through data stewardship services. Hence, both funding and policy support to recognise these efforts will be crucial to underpin EU policy on Open Science.

2.3. Funding of research infrastructures

Not applicable.

2.4. International co-operation of research infrastructures

To facilitate the development of community standards for image data and for AI models, the AI4Life project has coordinated interactions with various European RIs, like [Euro-BioImaging](#), [EU-OPENSCREEN](#), [Instruct-ERIC](#), [EMBRC](#), [EMPHASIS](#), and data-heavy RIs like [ELIXIR](#). Specific interactions with the international community were mediated through networks, like [Global BioImaging](#), [GloBIAS](#), [volumeEM](#), or the Euro-BioImaging-coordinated project, [foundingGIDE](#). Additionally, the project has partnered with research teams and organisations beyond Europe, such as [Bioimaging North America](#) (BINA), [Janelia](#) (e.g. COSEM) and the [BROAD Institute](#) to align on standards, avoid duplication of efforts, ensure cross-compatibility, and integrate new tools on a more global level. These interactions are summarised in [D7.2](#) (Report on AI4Life workshops, hackathons and communication activities with other Life Science RIs) and strongly underpin the EU policy on Open Science, supporting the development of image data as a global resource.

2.5. Employment and skills in research infrastructures

Throughout its lifetime, AI4Life organised diverse training activities including workshops, courses and hackathons for life science researchers, developers, as well as research infrastructure staff. These events aimed to enhance skills in using and developing AI methods and demonstrating how AI tools like the BioImage Model Zoo and the AI-ready datasets gallery at the BioImage Archive can improve image analysis processes, method development and research. In addition, the project developed community standards for image data and AI models, encouraging best practices and FAIR principles across the imaging and research communities. The skills and knowledge gained from AI4Life will continue to benefit research infrastructures beyond the project's lifetime, promoting future collaborations and building essential expertise.

2.6. Greening of research infrastructures

By promoting access to FAIR and standardised pre-trained AI models, AI4Life supports reproducible and efficient science and allows the reuse of scientific outputs, prolonging the utility of existing resources. In addition, by providing access to shared compute infrastructure to run the models in a user-friendly way, AI4Life promotes flexible usage of these resources, eliminating the need to duplicate infrastructure into local instances.

Furthermore, storing annotated images in the form of AI-ready datasets minimises the need to rerun resource-intensive models to produce outputs.

Recommendation 04: Incentivise the integration of energy-use and carbon-intensity monitoring into EOSC-related data centers and compute provider services to raise user awareness and support greener decision-making.

2.7. Interaction of research infrastructures with industry

AI4Life has built an active, bidirectional dialogue with key industry stakeholders. These include major actors in imaging and pharmaceuticals, such as Bayer, Zeiss, and Leica. Through these collaborations, AI4Life has promoted open standards, compatibility and interoperability at all levels and tried to engage industry partners to contribute to and freely consume all available analysis models (AI-based tools and methods) in the BMZ service portfolio. A prime example of these collaborations is the integration of several BMZ models into Leica's AIVIA microscopy image analysis software.

Challenges:

- Fragmented standards and proprietary formats and APIs make industry interactions difficult and time-consuming.
- Industry actors need long-term uptime, versioning and support that research infrastructures with project-based funding may rarely provide.

Recommendation 05: Provide dedicated, multi-year operational funding lines for serving research infrastructures so they can offer industry-grade services and long-term availability.

2.8. ERIC legal framework

Not applicable.

2.9. Technology development, data and digital services, digitalisation

Through the BMZ infrastructure services, the related standardisation of AI models and methods and the multifaceted training and outreach activities, AI-based methods will become an essential and easily accessible technology for cutting-edge, imaging-heavy life sciences research. New state-of-the-art methods will immediately propagate to the community and connect microscope and method developers to practitioners in research laboratories and facilities.

Recommendation 06: Provide dedicated programmes and resources to support and incentivise data and AI model reuse for improved, accelerated and sustainable technology and service developments.

Recommendation 07: Support collaborative community efforts to develop, promote, and maintain community-agreed data, metadata and model standards for interoperability and FAIR compliance, enhancing digital services and technology development.

2.10. Level of connection of your RI to EOSC

AI4Life supported and continues to support making image data FAIR and AI-ready through a community-driven process. Currently, such datasets are openly available through the BIA, while the guidelines, together with other project outputs, are indexed in the EOSC resources through [OpenAIRE](#). The project also facilitated active collaborations with other cross-domain data-driven and EOSC-related projects, like [iMagine](#), [ANERIS](#) or [RI-SCALE](#). A particular highlight is the collaboration between AI4Life and [AI4EOSC](#). This partnership enabled the successful integration of AI4Life resources with AI4EOSC's AI4OS platform, allowing users to launch BMZ image analysis models using AI4EOSC's computational resources and thus linking AI4Life services to the EOSC and enhancing EOSC adoption. In addition, the project partners Euro-BioImaging, EMBL and EMBL-EBI are working together with other RI partners to set up an EOSC Life Science Research (LSR) Node to offer their services through the EOSC with the potential of including services and resources developed through AI4Life.

Recommendation 08: Establishing mechanisms for accessing on-demand compute resources together with technical support and compute opportunities via the EOSC is important to sustain the AI4Life infrastructure that uses resources intensively, but often in bursts. Implementation of access beyond a basic compute contingent on a per-user basis via existing agreements or through compute tokens will need to be enabled to allow infrastructures like AI4Life to request compute contingents in their own name and distribute them fairly among their users.

2.11. Contribution to other research areas and to broader EU priorities

Not applicable.

2.12. Sustainability of research infrastructures

Throughout its lifespan, AI4Life has delivered diverse activities and outputs that directly support the long-term sustainability of its services. These include the development of community standards for image data, metadata and AI models, as well as the dissemination of FAIR guidelines and best practices, for example, in the context of Open

Calls. These efforts have not only enhanced the interoperability and usability of the infrastructure but also supported the continued use of the AI4Life services, contributing to the overall infrastructure sustainability.

The project has also placed strong emphasis on community building, engagement, and co-development of the AI4Life infrastructure together with the broader imaging and developer communities. This approach intends to make it a long-term effort continuing beyond the end of the project, that is not only for, but also driven by the community. By partnering with well-established European RIs like Euro-BioImaging and through the establishment of a community-inclusive AI4Life governance structure, the project aims to create a lasting ecosystem resilient to the ups and downs of project cycles.

Challenges:

- Need to constantly improve and develop the infrastructure services due to the fast-developing AI landscape and AI methodologies.

Recommendation 09: Offer long-term operational grants for serving research infrastructures, including service-level objectives, user support and helpdesk capacity.

Recommendation 10: Provide dedicated support and funding for community engagement and governance activities that empower user communities to co-develop and maintain the infrastructure.

